

Results on fixed points for WC-Mappings satisfying generalized contractive condition in C- metric spaces

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Abstract: In the present paper, we obtained a unique common fixed theorem for WC-mappings (WC-Weakly Compatible) for four self-mappings and also satisfying a generalized type of contractive condition in C- Metric Spaces (Cone-Metric Spaces). Our main aim is in this paper some of the well known results are extends, improves and generalizes , which are existing in the literature.

Key words: C-Metric Space(Cone Metric Space). Common fixed point, WC- mappings(Weakly Compatible-mappings).
AMS subject classifications: 47H10, 54H25.

1. Introduction

In the non-linear analysis the fixed point theory is one of the important branch. In 2007, Huang and Zhang [4] generalized the concept of a metric space and introduced a new concept, that is C-Metric Space (Cone-Metric Space), and they were replaced the real numbers by an ordered Banach space and also proved some fixed point theorems in C-Metric Space. Subsequently, many authors have been inspired by with these results they extended, improved and generalized in the different ways (see for e.g.,[1-3], [6-11]). Recently, Kumar and Gupta [6] proved a unique common fixed point theorem for two pairs of weakly compatible maps in cone metric spaces. In this paper, we obtained a unique common fixed point theorem for WC-mappings (WC- Weakly Compatible) for four self-mappings in C- Metric Spaces. Our aim is generalized the contractive condition and improve the results.

2. Preliminaries

The following are useful in our main results these are in [2, 4].

Definition 2.1. Let F be a real Banach space and Q be a subset of F . The set Q is called a cone iff

- (i). Q is closed, non-empty and $Q \neq \{0\}$;
- (ii). Let $\alpha, \beta \in R, \alpha, \beta \geq 0, u, v \in Q \implies \alpha u + \beta v \in Q$;
- (iii). $Q \cap (-Q) = \{0\}$.

For a given cone $Q \subseteq F$, we define a partial ordering " \leq " with respect to Q by $\alpha \leq \beta$ if and only if

$\beta - \alpha \in Q$. A cone Q is called normal if there exists $L > 0$ such that for all $\alpha, \beta \in Q$,

$$0 \leq \alpha \leq \beta \implies \|\alpha\| \leq L \|\beta\| \dots(A)$$

The least positive number L satisfying the above inequality is called the normal constant of Q . While $\alpha \ll \beta$ stands for $\beta - \alpha \in \text{int}Q$ (interior of Q).

Definition 2.2. Let X be a non empty set of F . Suppose that the map $\rho : X \times X \rightarrow F$ satisfies :

- (1) $0 \leq \rho(\alpha, \beta)$ for all $\alpha, \beta \in X$ and $\rho(\alpha, \beta) = 0$ if and only if $\alpha = \beta$;
- (2) $\rho(\alpha, \beta) = \rho(\beta, \alpha)$ for all $\alpha, \beta \in X$;
- (3) $\rho(\alpha, \beta) \leq \rho(\alpha, \gamma) + \rho(\beta, \gamma)$ for all $\alpha, \beta, \gamma \in X$.

Then ρ is called a cone metric on X and (X, ρ) is called a C-Metric Space(Cone Metric Space).

Definition 2.3. Let (X, ρ) be a C-metric space. We say that $\{x_n\}$ is

- (i) a Cauchy sequence if for every c in F with $0 \ll c$, there is N such that for all $n, m > N$, $\rho(x_n, x_m) \ll c$;
- (ii) a convergent sequence if for any $0 \ll c$, there is an N such that for all $n > N$, $\rho(x_n, x) \ll c$, for some fixed x in X . We denote this $x_n \rightarrow x$ ($n \rightarrow \infty$).

Definition 2.4. A C-Metric Space(Cone Metric Space) X is said to be complete if every Cauchy sequence in X is convergent in X .

Definition 2.5. Let A and B be two self maps of a set X . A point x in X are said to be WC- mappings (Weakly Compatible) if they are commute at their coincidence point of A and B , that is $Ax = Bx$ for some $x \in X$ then $ABx = BAx$.

Definition 2.6. A and B be two self-mappings of a set X . If $z = Ax = Bx$, for some $x \in X$, then x is called a coincidence point of A and B , where z is called coincidence point of coincidence of A and B .

3. Main Results

In this section, we prove a unique common fixed point theorem for WC-mappings for four self-mappings in C-Metric Spaces.

Now we prove our main theorem.

Theorem 3.1. Let (X, ρ) be a C-Metric Space(Cone Metric Space) and Q be a normal cone. Let A, B, M and N be self-mappings such that:

$$\rho(Mx, Ny) \leq \lambda_1 \rho(Ax, By) + \lambda_2 [\rho(Ax, Mx) + \rho(By, Ny)]/2 + \lambda_3 [\rho(Ax, Ny) + \rho(By, Mx)]/2. \quad (1)$$

For all $x, y \in X$, $\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \lambda_3 \geq 0$ and $\lambda_1 + \lambda_2 + \lambda_3 < 1$.

$$N(X) \subseteq A(X), M(X) \subseteq B(X) \text{ and one of } A(X) \text{ or } B(X) \text{ is a complete subspace of } X. \quad (2)$$

$$(A, M) \text{ and } (B, N) \text{ are weakly compatible.} \quad (3)$$

Then A, B, M and N have a unique common fixed point in X .

Proof. Let $x_0 \in X$. Define $y_{2n} = Mx_{2n} = Bx_{2n+1}$, $y_{2n+1} = Nx_{2n+1} = Ax_{2n+2}$.

Putting $x = x_{2n}$, $y = x_{2n+1}$, for all $n = 1, 2, \dots$. By (1) we get that

$$\begin{aligned}
 \rho(y_{2n}, y_{2n+1}) &= \rho(Mx_{2n}, Nx_{2n+1}) \\
 &\leq \lambda_1 \rho(Ax_{2n}, Bx_{2n+1}) + \lambda_2 [\rho(Ax_{2n}, Mx_{2n}) + \\
 &\quad \rho(Bx_{2n+1}, Nx_{2n+1})] / 2 + \lambda_3 [\rho(Ax_{2n}, Nx_{2n+1}) + \rho(Bx_{2n+1}, Mx_{2n})] / 2, \\
 &\leq \lambda_1 \rho(y_{2n-1}, y_{2n}) + \lambda_2 [\rho(y_{2n-1}, y_{2n}) + \rho(y_{2n}, y_{2n+1})] / 2 + \lambda_3 [\rho(y_{2n-1}, y_{2n+1}) + \rho(y_{2n}, y_{2n+1})] / 2, \\
 &\leq [\lambda_1 + \lambda_2 / 2 + \lambda_3 / 2] \rho(y_{2n-1}, y_{2n}) + [\lambda_2 / 2 + \lambda_3 / 2] \rho(y_{2n}, y_{2n+1}), \\
 &\leq \frac{[2\lambda_1 + \lambda_2 + \lambda_3] / 2}{[2 - (\lambda_2 + \lambda_3)] / 2} \rho(y_{2n-1}, y_{2n}), \\
 &\leq \frac{[2\lambda_1 + \lambda_2 + \lambda_3]}{[2 - (\lambda_2 + \lambda_3)]} \rho(y_{2n-1}, y_{2n}), \\
 \rho(y_{2n}, y_{2n+1}) &\leq \alpha \rho(y_{2n-1}, y_{2n}),
 \end{aligned}$$

where $\alpha = \frac{[2\lambda_1 + \lambda_2 + \lambda_3]}{[2 - (\lambda_2 + \lambda_3)]} < 1$.

Similarly, it can be shown that

$$\rho(y_{2n+1}, y_{2n+2}) \leq \alpha \rho(y_{2n}, y_{2n+1}).$$

Therefore, for all n

$$\rho(y_{n+1}, y_{n+2}) \leq \rho(y_n, y_{n+1}) \leq \dots \leq \alpha^{n-1} \rho(y_0, y_1).$$

Now for any m , $n \rightarrow \infty$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \rho(y_n, y_m) &\leq \rho(y_n, y_{n+1}) + \rho(y_{n+1}, y_{n+2}) + \dots \leq \rho(y_{m-1}, y_m). \\
 &\leq [\alpha^n + \alpha^{n-1} + \dots + \alpha^{m-1}] \rho(y_0, y_1). \\
 &\leq [\alpha^n / 1 - \alpha^n] \rho(y_0, y_1).
 \end{aligned}$$

From (A) we get that

$$\| \rho(y_n, y_m) \| \leq [\alpha^n / 1 - \alpha^n] L \| \rho(y_0, y_1) \|.$$

Which implies that $\rho(y_n, y_m) \rightarrow 0$ as $m, n \rightarrow \infty$.

Hence $\{y_n\}$ is a Cauchy sequence. Since X is complete, there exists a point $z \in X$ such that

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} y_{2n} = z.$$

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} Mx_n = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} Bx_{2n+1} = z \text{ and } \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} Nx_{2n+1} = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} Ax_{2n+2} = z.$$

That is $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} Mx_n = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} Bx_{2n+1} = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} Nx_{2n+1} = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} Ax_{2n+2} = z$.

Since $N(X) \subseteq A(X)$, there exists a point $u \in X$ such that $Au = z$. Then by (1) we get that

$$\begin{aligned}
 \rho(Mu, z) &\leq \rho(Mu, Nx_{2n-1}) + \rho(Nx_{2n-1}, z), \\
 &\leq \lambda_1 \rho(Au, Bx_{2n-1}) + \lambda_2 [\rho(Au, Mu) + \rho(Bx_{2n-1}, Nx_{2n-1})] / 2 \\
 &\quad + \lambda_3 [\rho(Au, Nx_{2n-1}) + \rho(Bx_{2n-1}, Mu)] / 2 + \rho(Nx_{2n-1}, z)
 \end{aligned}$$

From (A) we get that

$$\| \rho(Mu, z) \| \leq \lambda_1 K \| \rho(Au, Bx_{2n-1}) \| + \lambda_2 K \| [\rho(Au, Mu) + \rho(Bx_{2n-1}, Nx_{2n-1})]/2 \| + \lambda_3 K \| [\rho(Au, Nx_{2n-1}) + \rho(Bx_{2n-1}, Mu)]/2 \| + \| \rho(Nx_{2n-1}, z) \| .$$

Letting $n \rightarrow \infty$ we get that

$$\begin{aligned} \rho(Mu, z) &\leq \lambda_1 \rho(z, z) + \lambda_2 [\rho(z, z) + \rho(zz)]/2 + \lambda_3 [\rho(z, z) + \rho(z, Mu)]/2 + \rho(z, z), \\ &\leq [\lambda_2/2 + \lambda_3/2] \rho(Mu, z), \\ &\leq [\lambda_2 + \lambda_3]/2 \rho(Mu, z). \end{aligned}$$

which is a contradiction, because $\lambda_1 + \lambda_2 + \lambda_3 < 1$.

Therefore,

$$Mu = Au = z. \tag{4}$$

Since $M(X) \subseteq B(X)$, there exists a point $v \in X$ such that $Bv = z$. Then by (1) we get that

$$\begin{aligned} \rho(z, Nv) &= \rho(Mu, Nv) \\ &\leq \lambda_1 \rho(Au, Bv) + \lambda_2 [\rho(Au, Mu) + \rho(Bv, Nv)]/2 + \lambda_3 [\rho(Au, Nv) + \rho(Bv, Mu)]/2, \\ &\leq \lambda_1 \rho(z, z) + \lambda_2 [\rho(z, z) + \rho(z, Nv)]/2 + \lambda_3 [\rho(z, Nv) + \rho(z, z)]/2, \\ &\leq [\lambda_2/2 + \lambda_3/2] \rho(z, Nv), \\ \rho(z, Nv) &\leq [\lambda_2 + \lambda_3]/2 \rho(z, Nv), \end{aligned}$$

which is a contradiction, because $\lambda_1 + \lambda_2 + \lambda_3 < 1$.

Therefore,

$$Nv = Bv = z. \tag{5}$$

Since, A and M are WC-mappings (Weakly Compatible), then $MAu = AMu$ that is, $Mz = Az$.

Now we shall prove that, z is a fixed point of M . If $Mz \neq z$, then by (1) we get that

$$\begin{aligned} \rho(Mz, z) &= \rho(Mz, Nv) \\ &\leq \lambda_1 \rho(Az, Bv) + \lambda_2 [\rho(Az, Mz) + \rho(Bv, Nv)]/2 + \lambda_3 [\rho(Az, Nv) + \rho(Bv, Mz)]/2, \\ &\leq \lambda_1 \rho(Mz, z) + \lambda_2 [\rho(Mz, Mz) + \rho(z, z)]/2 + \lambda_3 [\rho(Mz, z) + \rho(z, Mz)]/2, \\ &\leq [\lambda_1 + \lambda_3] \rho(Mz, z), \end{aligned}$$

which is a contradiction, because $\lambda_1 + \lambda_2 + \lambda_3 < 1$.

Therefore,

$$Mz = z. \tag{6}$$

Similarly, B and N are WC-mappings (Weakly Compatible), we have, $Nz = Bz$.

Now we shall prove that, z is a fixed point of N . If $Nz \neq z$, then by (1) we get that

$$\begin{aligned} \rho(z, Nz) &= \rho(Mz, Nz) \\ &\leq \lambda_1 \rho(Az, Bz) + \lambda_2 [\rho(Az, Mz) + \rho(Bz, Nz)]/2 + \lambda_3 [\rho(Az, Nz) + \rho(Bz, Mz)]/2, \\ &\leq \lambda_1 \rho(z, Nz) + \lambda_2 [\rho(z, z) + \rho(Nz, Nz)]/2 + \lambda_3 [\rho(z, Nz) + \rho(Nz, z)]/2, \\ &\leq [\lambda_1 + \lambda_3] \rho(z, Nz), \end{aligned}$$

which is a contradiction , because $\lambda_1 + \lambda_2 + \lambda_3 < 1$.

Therefore,

$$Nz = z. \quad (7)$$

Thus, $Mz = Nz = Az = Bz = z$, that is z is a common fixed point of A, B, M and N .

Uniqueness: Suppose z_1 is a common fixed point of A, B, M and N . Then by (1), we get that

$$\begin{aligned} \rho(z, z_1) &= \rho(Mz, Nz_1) \\ &\leq \lambda_1 \rho(Az, Bz_1) + \lambda_2 [\rho(Az, Mz) + \rho(Bz_1, Nz_1)]/2 + \lambda_3 [\rho(Az, Nz_1) + \rho(Bz_1, Mz)]/2, \\ &\leq \lambda_1 \rho(z, z_1) + \lambda_2 [\rho(z, z) + \rho(z_1, z_1)]/2 + \lambda_3 [\rho(z, z_1) + \rho(z_1, z)]/2, \\ &\leq [\lambda_1 + \lambda_3] \rho(z, z_1), \end{aligned}$$

which is a contradiction because $\lambda_1 + \lambda_2 + \lambda_3 < 1$.

Therefore, $z = z_1$.

Hence, z is a unique common fixed point of A, B, M and N .

This completes proof of the theorem. □

4. Conclusion

In this research article we generalized the contractive condition and proved generalized results, so that our results are more general improved than the results of [6].

Conflict of interest: The author has declared there is no conflict of interest.

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References

- [1] Abbas M and Jungck G, Common fixed point results for non commuting mappings without continuity in cone metric spaces, J. Math. Anal. Appl. 2008; 341: 416-420.
- [2] Abbas M, Rhoades B.E, Fixed and periodic point results in cone metric spaces, Appl. Math. Lett. 2008; 21: 511-515.
- [3] Guangxing Song, Xiaoyan Sun, Yian Zhao, Guotao Wang, New common fixed point theorems for maps on cone metric spaces, Appl. Math. Lett. 2010; 32:1033-1037.
- [4] Huang L G, Zhang X, Cone metric spaces and fixed point theorems of contractive mappings J. Math. Anal. Appl. 2007; 332(2): 1468-1476.
- [5] G. Junck and B.E. Rhoads, Fixed point forest valued functions without continuity, Indian J. Pure Appl. Maths. 1998 ; 29(3): 227-238.
- [6] R. Kumar and A. Gupta , A unique common fixed point theorem for two pairs of weakly compatible maps on cone metric spaces, International Journal of Engineering and Innovative Technology , 2013 ; Vol.3. , Issue 5: 407- 409.
- [7] Prudhvi K, A Unique Common Fixed Point Theorem for a Metric Space with the Property (E.A), American Journal of Applied Mathematics and Statistics, 2023; Vol.11., No.1: 11-12.
- [8] Prudhvi K, Generalized Fixed Points for Four Self – Mappings with the property OWC in CMS, Asian Research Journal of Mathematics, 2023; Vol.9, Issue. 5: 37- 40 .

- [9] Prudhvi K, Common fixed points on occasionally weakly compatible self-mappings in CMS, Asia Matematika, 2023 ; Vol.7, Issue.2:13-16.
- [10] Prudhvi K, Study on Fixed Points for OWC in Symmetric Spaces, Asia Matematika, 2023 ; Vol.7, Issue 3: 72- 75.
- [11] Zhang X, Common fixed point theorems for some new generalized contractive type mappings, J. Math. Anal. Appl.2007;333: 780-786.